

Air Pollution in Nigeria: An Overview of Regulatory Challenges and Strategies

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Abstract:

Air pollution results from the direct or indirect release of harmful substances or energy into the atmosphere, posing severe risks to human health, ecosystems, and environmental use. In Nigeria, it is the fourth leading cause of mortality, responsible for over 7% of deaths. Globally, initiatives such as treaties, conventions, and protocols have sought to address the issue, but progress has been hampered by the transboundary nature of pollution, fragmented frameworks, conflicting development priorities, weak enforcement, inadequate technology, and funding constraints. Domestically, Nigeria has attempted regulation through the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act 2007, the Climate Change Act 2021, and the Petroleum Industry Act. However, these measures face challenges including weak institutional capacity, overlapping mandates, corruption, poor enforcement, limited public awareness, reliance on polluting industries, and outdated infrastructure. Using doctrinal analysis, the study finds that both global and Nigerian frameworks lack effective technological monitoring systems, coordination, and modern enforcement strategies. It recommends stronger international laws, capacity building, real-time emissions tracking, open databases, and technology transfer globally. For Nigeria, the paper emphasizes legal harmonization, stronger institutions, judicial reforms, public participation, and adoption of modern monitoring technologies.

Keywords: Air Pollution, Transboundary, Ecosystem, Regulation, Challenges, Strategies, Nigeria.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is one of the four categories of recognized pollution in Nigeria under Section 20 of the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act 2007 (as amended). It results in physical harm, loss of value, or injury to the atmosphere, living organisms, and the environment. While air pollution may arise from both natural disasters and human activities, scholarly consensus identifies human activities as the dominant source¹ Continuous pollution leads to environmental degradation, diminishes ecological balance, and in severe cases, threatens species with extinction. Globally, statistics show that 4.3 million people die prematurely each year from indoor pollution caused by unsustainable cooking and heating fuels². In Nigeria, air pollution ranks as the fourth leading mortality risk, accounting for over 7% of deaths (114,100) in 2017 alone³. Reports further indicate that Nigeria is the 10th most polluted country in Africa, with a pollution rate of 44.8%, followed closely by Uganda and Ethiopia. Combined effects of outdoor and indoor pollution are linked to over seven million premature deaths annually.

The impacts of air pollution include climate change, flash floods, erratic rainfall, and the endangerment or extinction of wildlife species. In response, several global initiatives have emerged, such as the Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer, the Montreal Protocol, the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the Kyoto Protocol, the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP), and the 2015 Paris Agreement. Additionally, the 2015 WHO Air Quality Guidelines provide international standards for reducing health risks from air pollution. Nigeria's efforts to regulate air quality are reflected in the Criminal Code, the NESREA Act and its regulations, the Petroleum Industry Act 2021, the Climate Change Act 2021, and common law principles of nuisance, negligence, and trespass. This paper therefore seeks to examine both global initiatives on air pollution control and Nigeria's regulatory framework, highlighting enforcement challenges and proposing solutions for improved effectiveness. Using a doctrinal methodology, it critically analyzes international efforts, their influence on Nigeria, and Nigeria's own initiatives. It also engages relevant literature and draws insights from developed countries' regulatory systems to suggest lessons applicable to Nigeria.

¹ V.O. Aigbokhaevbo, *Climate Change in Nigeria: Cases and Materials* (University of Nigeria Press, 2023) 5;

² AEA Okposin, "Nigeria and the Sustainable Development Goal on 'Energy Access' by 2030: Prospects and Challenges" *Commemorative Essays for the 60th Anniversary of the Faculty of Law, University of Nigeria, Nsukka*

(Faculty of Law, University of Nsukka, Enugu Campus, Enugu State, 2021) 441-469.

³ Health Effects Institute; Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. *The State of Air Quality and Health Impacts in*

Africa. A report from the state of Global Air initiative; 2022. In fact, the report has it that air pollution is the

fourth leading cause of death globally, accounting for nearly 7 million deaths annually>state of global Air+1>

accessed

17/09/2025.

For clarity, the paper is organized into various sections which introduce the article, and address the concept of air pollution in Nigeria, efforts at controlling air pollution, challenges, and conclusion.

2. THE CONCEPT OF AIR POLLUTION

The Convention on Long Range Transboundary Air Pollution 1979, in its article 1, defined air pollution as:

The introduction by man, directly or indirectly of substance of energy into the air, resulting in deleterious effect of such a nature as to endanger human health, farming, living resources and ecosystems and material property, and to cause an impairment or to interfere with amenities and other legitimate use of the environment.

From the definition above, air pollution is caused by natural processes like volcanic eruptions and man's activities. However, the Nigeria's main regulatory agency on air pollution, National Environmental Standard Regulatory Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act 2007 (as amended) does not define air pollution, but only 'pollution' generally as 'man-made or man aided alteration or chemical, physical, or biological quality of the environment beyond acceptable limits.'⁴ Under section 20, of the Act, the Agency is empowered to make regulations setting specifications and standards to protect and enhance the quality of Nigeria's air resources so as to promote public health, welfare and natural development and productivity capacity of the nation. The section also prescribes penalties for violations of regulations made by the Agency. Before discussing the regulations in depth, it is pertinent to discuss briefly the meaning of air and its components in order to appreciate the quality of air for a healthy living and sustainable environment.

The Merriam-Webster defines air as the mixture of invisible odourless, tasteless gases (such as nitrogen and oxygen) that surrounds the earth.⁵ Air consists of 78% nitrogen, 21% oxygen and 1% other gases including water vapour.⁶ It is important to note that activities from land, sea and the atmosphere interfere with the natural constituents of the gases that made up air and alter its composition, thereby polluting the air.⁷

2.1 Causes of air pollution

Air pollution is caused by both natural or primary sources and human activities or secondary sources.

(a) The Natural sources include:

⁴ NESREA Act, Section 37

⁵ Merriam-Webster see <https://merriam-webster.com> accessed 23/0/23.

⁶ See constituents of air –<https://byjus.com>> accessed 23/05/23.

⁷ L. Atsegbua, V. Akpotaire and F. Dimowo, *Environmental Law in Nigeria: Theory and Practice* (New edn, Ambic Press 2009) 103;

- (i) Volcanic eruptions- which occur when magma (molten rock) from beneath the earth's surface is released through a vent or fissure.⁸
 - (ii) Wildfires: These are uncontrolled fires that occur in wild land areas, often triggered by natural causes such as lightening, drought, or heat waves⁹.
 - (iii) Dust storms: These are natural events that occur when strong winds pick up large amounts of dry soil or sand particles, examples include, the Arizona Haboobs (USA), Australian Dust Storms, Middle Eastern Sandstorms, African Dust Storms and Chinese Dust Storms¹⁰; and
 - (iv) Natural gas seeps: These refer to the release of natural gas from the Earth's crust, often through geological formations, faults or fractures example include the Gulf of Mexico (USA)-Hydrocarbon seeps; Sichuan Basin (China)-Natural gas seeps; Caspian Sea (EUROP/Asia)-Mud volcanoes¹¹.
- (b) Human activities: Examples include:
- (i) Burning of fossil fuels: The combustion of fossil fuels emits a large amount of Sulphur dioxide. Also, incomplete combustion of fossil fuels release carbon monoxide, which results in air pollution.¹²
 - (ii) Automobiles: The gases emitted from vehicles such as jeeps, trucks, cars, buses etc., pollute the environment. These gases are the major sources of greenhouse gases and results in diseases among individuals.¹³
 - (iii) Agricultural activities: During agricultural activities, ammonia, which is the most hazardous gases are emitted. Furthermore, insecticides, pesticides and fertilizers used for agricultural purposes emit harmful chemicals in the atmosphere, thereby contaminating the air.¹⁴

⁸ Francis Albarède, *Volcanology* (Cambridge University Press, 2009); Robert I. Tilling, *Volcanic Eruptions* (Elsevier, 2008); James H. Gilbert, "The Volcano: A Practical Guide" ((John Wiley & Sons 2015).

⁹ CE Reid, "Critical review of health impacts of wildfire smoke exposure," (2016) 50(19) *Environmental Science & Technology Journal* 1033-10403.

¹⁰ Dust Storms and Cardiovascular Mortality (2017) *Air Quality, Atmosphere and Health (AQAH)*.

¹¹ G. Etiope, "Natural gas seeps"(2015) 120(10) *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 6395-6411 doi: 10.1002/2015JBO12029.

¹² MC Hansen, et al., "Quantifying trends in atmospheric carbon dioxide" (2013)13(10) *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 075-5085. doi: 10.5194/acp-13-5075.

¹³ D. Sperling, & D. Gordon, "Two billion cars: Driving toward sustainability" (Oxford University Press 2009) doi: 10.1093/acprof.oso/9780195374016.001.0001.

¹⁴ HJ Godfray, et al, "Food Security: The Challenge of feeding 9 billion people", (2010) 327(5967) *Science* 812-818, doi:10.1126/science.1185383.

- (iv) Factories and industries: Carbon monoxide, organic compounds, hydrocarbons and chemicals are release from the processes taking place in factories and industries, which are released into the air, thereby degrading its quality.¹⁵
- (v) Mining activities: During the mining process, the minerals below the earth are extracted using large pieces of equipment. The dust and chemicals apart from polluting the air also deteriorate the health of the workers and people living in the nearby areas.¹⁶
- (vi) Domestic sources: Household cleaning products and paints contain toxic chemicals that are released into the air. The smell from the newly painted walls is the smell of the chemicals present in the paints. It does not only affect the air but also affects breathing.¹⁷

2.2 Effects of Air Pollution

The effects of include:

- (a) Diseases: Long term health effects from air pollution include heart disease, lung cancer, and respiratory diseases such as emphysema. Air pollution can also cause long-term damage to people's nerves, brain, kidneys, liver, and other organs. Some scientists suspect air pollutants cause birth defects.¹⁸ Statistics from WHO has it that about 7 million people die each year from air pollution. More than 4,000 people died in just a few months due to a severe smog event that occurred in London in 1952.¹⁹
- (b) Harm to animals and plants: Wild life can experience many of the same negative health effects of air pollution that humans do. Damage to respiratory systems is the most common effect on animals. Others include neurological problems and skin irritations. On plants, it grows less with lesser fruits when exposed to long-term air pollution. Ozone pollution harm plants by damaging structures called stomata, which are tiny pores on the underside of leaves that allow the plant to 'breathe.' Some types of plants can protect themselves by temporarily closing their stomata or producing antioxidants, but others are particularly sensitive to damage. Between 1980 and 2011, 9 billion dollars-worth of soybeans and corn were lost in the US as a result of ozone pollution.²⁰ When acid rain, lead toxicity, and exposure to nitrogen oxides change the chemical nature of the soil, plants are robbed of the nutrients that they need to grow and survive, thus impacting negatively on

¹⁵ EPA, "National Emissions Inventory"(2022) 72(1) *Journal of the Air and Waste Management Association* 1-12

¹⁶TP Mernagh, "Environmental impact of mining" *Journal of Environmental Science and Health*, part C, 31, 147-162.

¹⁷TM Letcher, & DA Vallero, "Domestic pollution sources and impacts" (2011) part C 29(2) *Journal of Environmental Science and Health* 137-154.

¹⁸ Effects of Air Pollution,>[https:// national geography.org](https://nationalgeography.org)> accessed 9/6/2023; World Health Organization, "Health consequences of air pollution on populations">[https://www.who.int news item](https://www.who.int/news/item)>accessed 9/6/2023

¹⁹ Center for Science Education, "Effects of Air Pollution">scied.ucar.edu accessed 9/6/2023.

²⁰ Ibid.

agriculture, forests and grasslands. Other ways air pollution affects living things are damaging of habitat, water, and food sources that plants and animals need to survive.²¹

- (c) **Causing of Acid Rain:** Burning fossil fuels releases sulfur and nitrogen oxides into the atmosphere. Acid rain forms when sulfur dioxide mixes with water droplets in the atmosphere to make sulfuric acid and nitric acid. Winds can carry these pollutants for thousands of miles until they fall to the Earth's surface as acid rain, which damages the leaves of vegetation, increases the acidity of soils and water, and is linked to over 000 deaths each year. Buildings and other structures are also impacted by acid rain, which causes an estimated five billion dollars of property damage each year.²² Acid rain dissolves mortar between bricks, causes stone foundations to become unstable, and is destroying ancient buildings and statues carved from marble and limestone.²³
- (d) **Reducing Sunlight:** High levels of particulate pollution from all types of burning reduces the amount of sunlight that reaches the surface and even changes the appearances of the sky. When less sunlight is available for photosynthesis, forests grow at a slower rate and crops are less productive. Hazy skies not only reduce visibility but also impact the weather and even the climate.
- (e) **Making a hole in the Ozone Layer:** The hole in the ozone layer is caused by air pollutants. Chemicals used as refrigerants, such as chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), contain chlorine atoms. Releasing chlorine atoms into the atmosphere destroys ozone. A single chlorine atom can destroy thousands of ozone molecules. The ozone layer blocks harmful Ultraviolet-B (UVB) radiation from the sun, which protect us in a way that is similar to putting sunscreen on your skin to prevent sunburn. The ozone hole puts all living things at a risk by increasing the amount of UVB that reaches the surface. Exposure to UVB increases the risk of skin cancer in humans, restricts growth and development in plants, slows the development of fish and amphibians, and reduces the amount of phytoplankton in marine ecosystems. UVB also causes natural and synthetic materials to breakdown at an accelerated rate.²⁴
- (f) **Adding too much Nitrogen to Land:** Gaseous ammonia (NH₃) from agriculture and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) from car, truck, and airplane emissions increase the amount of nitrogen in soils. Plants need nitrogen to grow, but too much nitrogen can limit the growth of some plants and increase the growth of others, disrupting the balance of species within an ecosystem. This disruption is negatively impacting the grasslands and other fragile environments around the world²⁵.

²¹ Ibid.

²² Ibid.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

- (g) Causes Greenhouse Gas effects: Greenhouse gas, a product of air pollution is dangerous both to human health and the environment.

In effect, air pollution affects both human health and the environment. On human health, many of the greenhouse gases directly target the human respiratory system causing bronchitis and asthma. Some affect the central nervous system and the immune system, while others are reported to be carcinogenic and even cause death.²⁶ On the environment, it alters the planet's climate, leading to shifts in snow and rainfall patterns, a rise in average temperatures and more extreme climate events such as heatwaves and floods.²⁷ In other words, the greenhouse gas causes climate changes, causing the ecosystems to change faster than plants and animals can adapt resulting in the extinction of many species. Ordinarily, the greenhouse gases generally, help keep the Earth at a habitable temperature, but when it is too much, it absorbs the infrared radiation meant as natural shield, thereby trapping and holding heat in the atmosphere that causes global warming.²⁸

3. EFFORTS AT CONTROLLING AIR POLLUTION

The efforts at controlling air pollution shall be discussed under two sub-headings: international or regional, and domestic.

3.1 International and regional measures in controlling air pollution

Some of the measures taken globally in controlling air pollution were majorly initiative of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and they include:

(a) Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer

This is one of the most important international agreements, and it relates directly to global efforts at controlling air pollution caused by ozone-depleting substances (ODS). The Convention was adopted in Vienna, Austria, in 1985 under the UNEP and entered into force in 1988. It was a response to growing scientific evidence that man-made chemicals (like CFCs, halons, and carbon tetrachloride) were destroying the stratospheric ozone layer, which protects life on earth from harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The objectives were to promote cooperation among nations in research, monitoring, and information exchange on the ozone layer and to develop international measures to protect human health and the environment against adverse effects of ozone depletion. Sadly, the convention failed to set binding targets for reducing ozone –depleting substances but only created a framework for countries to cooperate and to later negotiate specific commitments.²⁹ Nigeria is a signatory to the convention having given her approval to the Convention on 31st of October 1988, by signing and ratifying it.

²⁶ United Nations Report > <https://www.un.org> ; British Geological Survey > <https://www.bgs.ac.uk> > accessed 24/07/2023

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ LAW GLOBAL HUB > lawglobalhub.com > accessed 25/07/2023; Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer (1985), United Nations Treaty Series, Vol. 1513, p. 293 > <https://treaties.un.org> > accessed 03/09/2025.; IH Rowlands, *The Politics of Global Atmospheric Change* (Manchester University Press 1993).

(b) Montreal Protocol (1987)

The Montreal Protocol on substances that deplete the Ozone Layer (1987) is a protocol under the Vienna Convention. While the Vienna Convention established cooperation and commitment, the Montreal Protocol provided legally binding targets for phasing out ODS³⁰. The Vienna Convention did not directly cut emissions, but it paved the way for the Montreal Protocol, it created a global consensus that ozone –depleting substances (ODS) like CFCs, halons, and carbon tetrachloride were dangerous pollutants, without these no global emission reductions would have been possible. The Montreal Protocol, created a legally binding treaty that help to phase out nearly 100 ozone-depleting substances (ODS), every member of the UN ratified it (universal participation), introduced a “control schedule” to phase out CFCs, halons, carbon tetrachloride, methyl chloroform, HFCs, and later HFCs, however, enforcement is not comprehensive enough to eliminate illegal trade (Black markets) especially in some developing countries on CFCs and HFCs. Secondly, there is the issue of lack of capacity, particularly in some developing countries to effectively monitor and enforce the scheduled phase out of the ODS despite the multilateral Fund provision³¹.

(c) United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)

The Convention was signed at Rio in 1992 and entered into force on 21 March 1994. Its main purpose is to provide framework for international cooperation to combat climate change by stabilizing greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic (human caused) interference with the climate system. The convention with 198 parties is nearly universal is predicated on the principles of common but differentiated responsibilities (CBDR)-recognizing that all states are responsible for addressing climate change, but developed countries bear a heavier responsibility because of their historical emissions; precautionary principle-take action even if scientific certainty is not complete; and sustainable development-integrating climate action with development goals.

Although the convention does not directly regulate air pollutants like sulfur dioxide (SO₂) nitrogen, oxides (NO_x), or particulate matter that most people think of when discussing air quality. Instead, its main focus is on greenhouse gases (GHGs) such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), which drive climate change but are not toxic in the same way as smog-forming pollutants. However, the UNFCCC process has indirectly improved air quality by providing policies for phasing out fossil fuels under Kyoto, Paris, and national climate plans that encourage renewable energy, energy efficiency and cleaner transport; technology shifts through promotion of electric vehicles, low carbon technologies, and better fuel standards which leads to cleaner

³⁰ Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer (1987), United Nations Treaty Series, Vol. 1522, p.3 > <https://ozone.unep.org> accessed 03/09/2025; RE Benedick, *Ozone Diplomacy: New Directions in Safeguarding the Planet* (Harvard University Press 1998, 2nd ed).

³¹ D Barack, *Illegal Trade in Ozone-Depleting Substances*, Chatham House Briefing Paper, Energy and Environment

Programme, Royal Institute of International Affairs; Environmental Investigation Agency (EIA), Report: The European Union’s Ozone Regulation and Illegal Trade in ODS, London: EIA; UNEP, *Evaluation of the Multilateral Fund for the Implementation of the Montreal Protocol*, Nairobi (2003).

air; and health outcomes through meeting Paris agreement targets, which could avoid millions of premature deaths attributable to air pollution³². The challenge(s) of the UNFCCC in improving air quality lies in the mandate gap-the UNFCCC is legally focused on greenhouse gases (GHGs), not traditional air pollutants like sulfur dioxide (SO₂) nitrogen, oxides (NO_x), or particulate matter (PM_{2.5}). Secondly, air-quality improvement is only a co-benefit of climate policies, not a primary objective. This weakens enforcement and reporting mechanisms on air pollution outcomes³³.

(d) The Kyoto Protocol

Kyoto Protocol in short, operationalizes the UNFCCC, by committing industrialized countries and economies in transition to limit and reduce greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions in accordance with agreed individual targets.³⁴ The Protocol seeks to regulate six greenhouse gases released through human activities, carbon dioxide (CO₂), Methane (CH₄), Nitrous Oxide (N₂O), Perfluorocarbons (PFCs), Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) and Sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆).³⁵

This was negotiated by 160 countries in December 1997, to provide a far more substantive framework for reducing GHG emissions. To achieve this, the Protocol initiated:

- (a) Emissions Trading among Annex 1 Countries (developed)
- (b) Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) under which Annex 1 countries invest in emissions limitations and sink enhancement projects in developing countries to obtain certified emission reduction credits (ERCs) that count against their quantified emissions reduction and limitation commitments (QERLCs) obligations.

Although the protocol focused primarily on climate change than air pollution control per se, but many of the measures taken by the protocol help also to improve air quality, for instance, by reducing fossil fuel combustion, it lowers CO₂ and air pollutants (SO₂, NO_x, PM_{2.5}). Secondly, for promoting renewable energy, smog and acid rain precursors are reduced and finally, energy efficiency measures in the Protocol will help cut industrial and transport emissions. The challenge however, of the Kyoto Protocol to air quality is that the Kyoto Protocol major focus is on GHGs, air quality improvements were indirect. Secondly, the Kyoto Protocol has limited participation, some big emitters like USA never ratified, Canada withdrew, and global impact was reduced³⁶.

³² The World Health Organization reported at COP24 (2018) that achieving the Paris goals could save about one

million lives per year by 2025 through reduced air pollution alone; see also A Lancet Planetary Health modeling study (2018) which found that health co-benefits from reduced air pollution substantially outweigh the costs of achieving Paris-level targets. Globally benefit-to-cost ratios range from 1.4 to 2.45 depending on the scenario. These benefits are especially strong in China and India, where health co-benefits can fully offset mitigation costs> ScienceDirect< accessed 03/09/2025.

³³ NO Keohane & DG Victor, *The Evolution of the UNFCCC*, Annual Review of Environment and Resources, (2016) 41, 379-400- This study explains why the UNFCCC's design (sovereignty, consensus rules) limits enforceability and implementation leverage.

³⁴ "What is the Kyoto Protocol" > <https://unfccc.int> Kyoto protocol> accessed 7/9/2023.

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ A Haines & KR Smith, Health benefits of Climate Change Mitigation: The Case of air Pollution abatement, (2013) 374, *The Lancet* 2104-2114

(e) Long Range Trans-Boundary Air Pollution Convention (LRTAP) (1979)

This convention was adopted in 1979 under the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), it entered into force in 1983. It was the first international legally binding treaty to deal with air pollution crossing national boundaries. The convention objectives were to limit, reduce, and prevent air pollution including long-range transport (pollutants travelling hundreds/thousands of kilometers) and focused initially on acid rain caused by SO₂, and NO_x emissions. This convention significantly helps cut emissions by over 70-80% since 1980s, contributed to less acid rain, improved forest health, cleaner lakes and rivers and help shape EU air quality.

(f) The Paris Agreement

The Paris Agreement was adopted on 12 December 2015 at the 21st Conference of the Parties (COP21) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and entered into force on 4 November 2016. It represents the most comprehensive global framework to date for addressing climate change, with near-universal participation³⁷. The Agreement's overarching goal is to limit global average temperature rise to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels, while pursuing efforts to restrict warming to 1.5°C.³⁸ It also seeks to enhance climate resilience and promote low-carbon development pathways. The Agreement is the first universal and legally binding climate treaty where both developed and developing countries pledged to take climate action, reflecting a shift from the top-down binding targets of the Kyoto Protocol to a bottom-up pledge-and-review system.³⁹ Although the Paris Agreement is primarily focused on mitigating climate change by reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, but it also has significant co-benefits for air quality control. One, many of the major sources of GHGs (e.g., fossil fuel combustion, industrial processes, deforestation) also emit air pollutants like sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), particulate matter (PM), and volatile organic (VOCs). Secondly, by targeting GHG reduction, the Paris Agreement indirectly addresses air pollution control. Thirdly, improved air quality is seen as co-benefit of climate action. Finally, under the Paris agreement countries set their own emission reduction targets, many of which involve reducing fossil fuel use, transitioning to renewables, and adopting clean energy-all of which reduce local air pollution⁴⁰. Despite the positive impacts of the Paris Agreement towards air quality improvement, the Paris Agreement does not have specific binding commitments on air pollution-it only indirectly

³⁷ UNFCCC 2016.

³⁸ See article 2 of UNFCCC, 2015.

³⁹ R. Falkner, *The Paris Agreement and the New Logic of International Climate Politics* International Affairs,

(2016) 92(5), 1107-1125; World Health Organization. *Air Pollution and climate change: Two sides of the same*

coin. ((2018 Geneva:WHO).

⁴⁰ For example, China efforts to cut coal consumption as part of its NDC have also reduced urban smog;

A. Markandya, J. Sampedro, SJ Smith, Van Dingenen, R. Pizarro-Irizar, C. Art, & M. Gonzalez-Eguino, *Health co-benefits from airpollution and mitigation costs of the Paris Agreement: A modelling study* ((2018 , 2(3) The Lancet Planetay Health, e126-e133; D. Shindell, G. Faluvegi, K. Seltzer, & C. Shindell, *Quantified, Localized health benefits of accelerated carbon dioxide emissions. Nature Climate Change,* (2018. 8(4), 291-295

improves air quality. Moreover, some countries prioritize carbon reduction but may not align policies with local air quality regulations⁴¹. Furthermore, there exist implementation gaps due to strict enforcement, which may lead to persistent local air pollution, particularly in rapidly industrializing nations⁴².

3.2 National measures for control of air pollution

The national measures is principally that of Nigeria, except where references are made to other countries to buttress a point or for comparative analysis. They include:

(a) Provisions in the Criminal Code Act of Nigeria⁴³, particularly, section 247, which says:

Any person who vitiates the atmosphere in any place so as to make it noxious to the health of persons in general dwelling or carrying on business in the neighbourhood, or passing along a public way; or does any act which is, and which he knows or has reason to believe to be, likely to spread the infection of any disease dangerous to life, whether human or animal is guilty of a misdemeanor, and is liable to imprisonment for six months.

This section is located within chapter 23 of the Criminal Code of Nigeria, offences against Public Health, it aims to protect public health by penalizing actions that threaten environmental and human safety. Related provisions are section 245, which addresses fouling of water sources and section 248, on risks from white (yellow) phosphorus in matches.

Section 247 serves as a legal deterrent against factories, businesses, or individuals that burn waste, discharge harmful smoke, or emit toxic gases into the air. By criminalizing such pollution, it indirectly promotes cleaner industrial practices and healthier air in communities. Although the penalty is only six months imprisonment (light compared to environmental damage), the law provides a foundation for prosecuting air polluters.

(b) Provisions in NESREA Act 2007 (as amended)

NESREA is the main environmental enforcement agency. The Agency oversees compliance with environmental laws, treaties and regulations and her specific power over air quality standards include the enactment of:

I. National Environmental (Air Quality Control) Regulations, 2014

The regulation sets ambient air quality standards for Nigeria, and establishes permissible limits for key pollutants such as:

(a) Sulphur dioxide (SO₂)

⁴¹ For example, India renewable energy expansion helps reduce reliance on coal, though local air pollution challenges remain

⁴² In the European Union, climate policies under the Paris Agreement overlap with strict air quality directives.

⁴³ Cap C38, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004.

- (b) Nitrogen oxides (NO_x)
- (c) Carbon monoxide (CO)
- (d) Ozone (O₃)
- (e) Particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5})
- (f) Volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Furthermore, the Regulations provide guidelines for monitoring reporting, and compliance.

This regulation has helped in improving air quality in Nigeria by requiring industries to obtain permits for operations and comply with emission limits. As a result, some companies have invested in pollution control technologies (e.g., filters, scrubbers) to avoid penalties. Despite this positive impacts, NESREA's weak enforcement capacity is a major draw-back. The Agency has limited manpower and monitoring equipment and has few air quality monitoring stations, mainly scattered in major cities, leaving rural and industrial areas unchecked.

Secondly, the Agency outdated infrastructure and data gaps is another major challenge. The Agency lack real-time nationwide air monitoring systems and data on pollutants is often outdated, inconsistent, or inaccessible to the public. Thirdly, many industries in Nigeria still operate without permits or fail to meet standards and there still persist the problem of illegal gas flaring and uncontrolled emissions in industrial clusters (e.g., the Port Harcourt soot problem). Finally, public apathy, low awareness, political and economic constraints. Citizens rarely report violations or demand enforcement; many see air pollution as "normal" or unavoidable. Also, pressure to attract investments often makes regulators reluctant to strictly enforce penalties and also limited government funding for environmental monitoring programs also add to the problem.⁴⁴

II. National Environmental (Control of Vehicular Emissions from Petrol and Diesel Engines) Regulations, 2011.

The regulation was enacted to control and reduce air pollution from vehicle sources; ensure vehicles comply with national air quality standards; protect public health and the environment from harmful emissions such as carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides

⁴⁴ AS Afolabi, & R. Adeola, *Air quality management in Nigeria: "Regulatory frameworks and enforcement challenges"*. (2020) 22(3) *Environmental Law Review* 210-225; CL Eze, & C. Chukwu, "The effectiveness of the

National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) in controlling air pollution in

Nigeria" (2019) 9(2) *Journal of Environmental Management and Policy*, 45-61; O. Okonkwo, & T. Arowolo,

"Urban air pollution in Nigeria: Policy gaps and enforcement limitations under NESREA regulations" (2021)1(1)

African Journal of Environmental Law and Policy 55-74; MC Onyema, "An appraisal of Nigeria's National

Environmental (Air Quality Control) Regulations, 2014 in the context of sustainable development" (2018) 9(1)

Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence, 112-130; see also, NESREA (2014).

National Environmental (Air Quality Control) Regulations, S.I. No. 11 of 2014. Abuja: Federal Government

Printer.

(NO_x), hydrocarbons (HC), sulphur oxides (SO_x), and particulate matter⁴⁵. The regulation applies to all vehicles operating on petrol or diesel engines within Nigeria; importation, sale, registration, and use of such vehicles; motor vehicles assembly plants, workshops, and testing centres. Furthermore, the regulation prescribes maximum permissible emission limits for pollutants from petrol and diesel engines, and standards set are aligned with international best practices (comparable with Euro standards but tailored for Nigeria) among others.

The significance of the regulation to air quality standard in Nigeria is that it helps the country tackle urban air pollution, especially in major cities like Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt. Secondly, it helps in reducing respiratory illnesses and environmental degradation and aligns the country with global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the transport sector⁴⁶. Despite the good intention of this regulation to address transport-related air pollution, it has faced several implementation challenges that limits its impact on air quality in Nigeria, some of which include, weak enforcement due to lack of adequate technical manpower, testing equipment, and monitoring facilities across the country. Secondly, the poor fuel quality in the country with sulphur contents of 3,000 ppm in diesel against the 50ppm in EU standards is a big challenge as dirty fuel undermines the effectiveness of emission controls, especially for diesel engines. Thirdly, Nigeria is like a dumping depot to second hand vehicles, many of which are old and already high emitters. Fourthly, the country has weak roadworthiness enforcement which focuses more on mechanical safety and certification than emission standards. Finally, Nigeria has low public awareness of the emission regulation and health impacts of vehicular emissions made worse with institutional overlaps without proper coordination. We have NESREA, Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) and state vehicle inspection Offices performing similar functions, these duplication cause confusion and gaps in enforcement.

⁴⁵ See National Environmental (Control of Vehicular Emissions from Petrol and Diesel Engines) Regulations, 2011

(No. 20 of 2011, Schedule 1 (Applicable from 28 April 2011) for emission limits based on reference mass (rm)

categories; schedule vii for Diesel Engines. For Petrol Engines: Emission limits are defined clearly by reference

mass-CO and HC+NO_x limits as contained in schedule. For Diesel Engines, specific engine emission figures are not

available from the accessible schedule; however, fuel sulfur limits are known (3,000 ppm diesel, 1,000 ppm

petrol

⁴⁶ A. Adebajo, "Environmental Regulation of Vehicle Emissions in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects" (2018) 12 (2)

Nigerian Law and Practice Journal 45; A. Okorie, 'Vehicular Emission Control and Air Quality in Nigeria: An

Appraisal of NESREA's Regulatory Framework' (2019) 7(1) *NIALS Journal of Environmental Law* 101; United

Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), *Low Sulphur Fuels and Vehicle Emission Standards: Global Experiences*

and Policy Options for Nigeria (UNEP 2016); CCAC (Climate and Clean Air Coalition), *Nigeria: Supporting Cleaner*

Fuels and Vehicle Emission Standards CCAC 2020) > <https://www.ccacoalition.org/partners/nigeria> > accessed 06/09/2025

III. National Environmental (Control of Bush and Forest Fire and Open Burning) Regulations, 2011

The regulation aims to prevent and control bush and forest fires; prohibit open burning of waste and other materials that pollute the atmosphere and protect ecosystems, human health, and property from fire hazards and harmful emissions. It applies to all individuals, communities, companies, and institutions in Nigeria; activities such as agricultural land clearing, waste disposal, forestry operations, industrial processes, and construction where burning is used.

The regulation if fully implemented will reduce air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions from indiscriminate burning; protects biodiversity in forests and farmlands, helps Nigeria meet international commitments (Paris Agreement, UNFCCC) on emission reductions and addresses major causes of desertification, soil erosion and loss of soil fertility in Northern and central Nigeria.⁴⁷ The challenges of this regulation in impacting air quality in Nigeria, apart from weak enforcement as a result of limited staff resources of NESREA, also include cultural and traditional practices as bush farming is widely used by farmers for land clearing with the believed to improve soil fertility. Others are poverty and lack of alternative. Farmers and rural dwellers lack access to mechanical land-clearing tools or affordable waste disposal methods; weak waste management infrastructure-few cities in the country have proper waste collection, recycling, or landfills, pushing residents to resort to open burning to dispose of refuse; climate and Environmental Factors-Nigeria's dry season (Harmattan) makes vegetation highly inflammable, which makes even small fires spreading uncontrollably, overwhelming enforcement agencies and finally, corruption and lack of political will is also a challenge. Weak political support for strict enforcement and tolerance of bush burning due to community resistance or political pressure challenge the effectiveness of the Regulation.⁴⁸

IV. National Environmental (Control of Fugitive Emissions from Cement Plants and Other Manufacturing Industries) Regulations, 2011

The regulation targets fugitive emissions (dust, smoke, vapours) from cement plants and industrial facilities. The regulation mandates installation of pollution control devices (electrostatic precipitators, filters) and also mandates industries to monitor and report air emissions. However, this regulation is challenged by weak enforcement by NESREA due to limited monitoring stations to track emissions, inconsistent enforcement, especially in remote industrial areas; high cost of pollution control technology e.g., electrostatic precipitators, fabric filters, scrubbers), which are very expensive; poor maintenance culture even where equipment exists; industry resistance-as cement companies argue that strict compliance raises production cost and inadequate Data and

⁴⁷ National Environmental (Control of Bush/Forest Fire and Open Burning) Regulations, S.1 No. 15 of 2011, Federal

Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette No. 58, Vol. 98, 20 July 2011

⁴⁸ A. Adegoke, "Challenges of Controlling Open Burning in Nigeria: The Role of NESREA" (2015) 9(2) *NIALS Journal of Environmental Law* 55; A. Okorie, 'Environmental Regulation and the Menace of Bush Burning in Nigeria: Legal and Institutional Perspectives' (2017) 5(1) *African Journal of Environmental Law and Policy* 86; World Bank, *Nigeria: Forest Fires, Land Degradation, and Air Quality Impacts* (World Bank Report 2018)

Monitoring-few continuous emission monitoring systems (CEMS) are installed in plants⁴⁹.

V. National Environmental (Ozone Layer Protection) Regulations, 2009

The Regulation was designed to give effect to Nigeria's obligations under the Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer (1985) and the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer (1987). The objectives include to prohibit the importation, manufacture, sale, and use of ozone-depleting substances (ODS); to ensure compliance with international agreements on the phase-out of ODS., and to protect human health and the environment from the harmful effects of ozone layer depletion. The regulation makes room for licensing system for the production and trade of ODS alternatives and prescribed standards for acceptable alternatives to ODS. Non-compliance attracts fines, suspension of permits, or imprisonment⁵⁰. This regulation is very significant to air quality control as ODS contribute to the depletion of the ozone layer by increasing ultra- violet (UV) radiation which has indirect impacts on air quality, human health (skin cancers, cataracts), and ecosystems. Consequently, by regulating and phasing out ODS, Nigeria contributes to global air quality improvement and climate protection, since many ODS are also potent greenhouse gases.

The challenge however, for the effectiveness of this regulation includes:

- (a) Weak enforcement capacity: NESREA and customs authorities often lack adequate manpower, monitoring equipment, and funding to effectively police borders and markets. This makes it difficult to stop illegal importation of banned ozone-depleting substances (ODS).
- (b) Smuggling and illegal trade: This is made possible as a result of porous borders, which allows banned ODS such as CFCs to still find their way to Nigeria's markets.
- (c) High cost of alternatives-environmentally friendly refrigerants, fire suppression systems, and related equipment are often expensive.
- (d) Poor public awareness: Many technicians and end-users are not fully aware of the environmental and health risks of ODS.
- (e) Limited industrial transition: Some industries (especially in refrigeration, aerosols, and solvents) still rely on ODS-dependent technologies. The reason may be due to high cost of investment in new technology, which many companies resist⁵¹.

Additional air quality control regulations by NEASREA include:

⁴⁹ National Environmental (Control of fugitive Emissions from Cement Plants and Other Manufacturing Industries) Regulations, S.1 No. 19 of 2011, Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette No. 47, Vol. 98, 17 May 2011; Eneh, O.C. 'Cement Production and Environmental Health Risks in Nigeria: Challenges for Sustainable Regulation' (2015) 7(2) *African Journal of Environmental Law and Policy* 88.

⁵⁰ National Environmental (Ozone-Layer Protection) Regulations, 2009, S.1, No. 32, Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, No. 58, Vol. 96, 28th August, 2009; Federal Ministry of Environment, *National Implementation Plan on Phase-out of Ozone Depleting Substances*, Abuja. FME, 2010

⁵¹ G. Adeola, "Environmental Policy and Problem of Enforcement in Nigeria." (2011) 1 (3) *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 121-129; S.A. Okecha, "The Challenges of Ozone Layer Protection in Developing Countries: A Case Study of Nigeria"(2019) 3(1) *Nigerian Journal of Environmental Law*, 77-96; United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), *Assessment Report on the Effects of Ozone Layer Depletion* (Nairobi:UNEP, 2018)

- a. National Environmental (Chemicals, Pharmaceuticals, Soaps and Detergent Manufacturing Industries) Regulations 2009. This regulation controls emissions.
- b. National Environmental (Standards for Telecommunications and Broadcast Facilities) Regulations, 2011. The Regulation addresses air and noise pollution from generators used in telecom masts and broadcast facilities and mandates emissions standards standby diesel and petrol generators.
- c. National Environmental (Base Metals, Iron and Steel Manufacturing/Recycling Industries Sector) Regulations, 2011. This regulation controls air emissions such as dust, smoke, and toxic gases from metal processing and recycling and requires emission reduction technology and monitoring.
- d. National environmental (Mining and Processing of Coal, Ores and Industrial Minerals) Regulations, 2009. This regulation control dust, smoke, and gaseous emissions from mining operations and requires protective measures for workers and nearby communities.
- e. National Environmental (Noise Standards and Control) Regulations, 2009. This regulation focuses on noise pollution, it addresses community health impacts linked to air pollution sources (e.g., power generators, factories, traffic).

The key challenges of these additional NESREA air quality regulations like the ones discussed before include weak enforcement, difficulty of monitoring thousands of dispersed facilities (e.g., telecommunication masts), corruption, low awareness, over dependence on diesel and petrol generators and social resistance.

VI. Associated Gas (Re-injection (Continued Flaring of Gas) Act 2010 (As Amended)⁵²

This Act is a key law regulating the handling of natural gas produced alongside crude oil (known as associated gas). It directly affects air quality because of its relationship with gas flaring, a major source of air pollution in Nigeria. This Act was originally enacted in 1979 and strengthened in later amendments and requires oil companies to submit programs for gas-re-injection rather than simply flaring associated gas. The 2010 amendment tightened restrictions by setting deadlines and penalties for continued gas flaring.

The relationship of this Act to air quality can be seen in the facts that gas flaring releases carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and particulate matter, all of which deteriorate air quality. Prolonged exposure to these pollutants causes respiratory illnesses, skin conditions, eye irritation, and cardiovascular diseases in host communities. Also, black carbon (soot) from flaring contributes to regional haze and worsens climate impacts by absorbing solar radiation. The Act therefore, by mandating gas utilization projects (such as liquefied natural gas (LNG), gas to power, and petrochemical (feedstock), the Act aims to reduce flaring and emissions, thereby improving ambient air quality. Disappointingly, the challenge of weak enforcement that still makes the country top gas-flaring countries globally has eroded the good purpose of the Act. Secondly, the provision which enables oil companies to obtain ministerial permits to flare gas, undermines the effectiveness of the Act. Thirdly, high cost

⁵² CapA25 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2010.

of gas capture and infrastructure (pipelines, processing facilities pose huge financial barrier⁵³.

(c) Control measures under the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) 2021

The PIA is Nigeria's most comprehensive oil and gas law, and while it is mainly about governance, revenue, and investment, it has strong environmental and air quality implications. Section 104 of the Act, prohibits gas flaring or venting of natural gas except under permit issued by the commission. The section also mandates operators to pay penalties for flaring without approval, and provides that penalties are no longer deductible for tax purposes (closing loophole in earlier laws. Very importantly penalties collected are directed into the Midstream and Downstream Gas Infrastructure Fund for gas utilization projects, which can indirectly reduce air pollution.

Also, the provision for Environmental Remediation Fund, which covers soil, water, and air impacts caused by petroleum operations, pollution from refining, storage, and transport (soot, VOCs, sulfur dioxide) falls under remediation obligations. It is important to note that the PIA aligns petroleum operations with national environmental standards set by NESREA and other regulators. This includes compliance with air quality standards (e.g., National Environmental (Air Quality Control) Regulations 2011).

Although the PIA is fossil- fuel focused, it indirectly supports cleaner energy transition by encouraging gas utilization (LNG, CNG, LPG) over flaring. However, despite the PIA's provisions, gas flaring continues in the Niger Delta due to weak monitoring, insecurity, and political influence. Disappointingly, penalties still cheaper than compliance and most host communities are excluded from decision-making and still face daily exposure to soot and toxic emissions. Finally, we submit that the PIA overlaps with NESREA causing avoidable clashes on environmental jurisdiction, thereby weakening oversight⁵⁴.

(d) Climate Change Act 2021

The Nigeria's Climate Change Act was enacted in November 2021 and provides legal framework for mainstreaming climate change actions into Nigeria's development plans. It establishes a National council (NCCC) to coordinate policies across all sectors. Although it is not an 'air quality law' per se, but many of its provisions influence air pollution control in the following areas:

- I. The Act introduces five-year carbon budgets, which cap greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

⁵³ IM Ajogwu, AO Ameh, AG Ojochegbe., *An Examination of the Legislative Framework on Gas Flaring in Nigeria*, (2022) 1 (1) *American Journal of Society and Law*, 31-38 (2022); SE Imoisi and S Iyemeake, "Curbing Gas Flaring in Nigeria: Legislative and Judicial Response" (2024) 11 (5) *Current Journal of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences* 18: AE Adeoye, "A Review of the Environmental Impact of Gas Flaring on the Physiological Properties of Water, Soil and Air Quality in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria" (2022) *Earthline Journal of Chemical Sciences*. See also the Flare Gas (Prevention of Waste and Pollution) Regulations 2018, issued by the Minister of Petroleum Resources in 2018 under the Petroleum Act. The Regulation is also aimed at reducing routine gas flaring and promoting the use of flare gas for economic purposes (e.g., power generation, LPG, industrial use). It establishes the Nigerian Gas Flare Commercialization programme which if effectively handled can directly reduce emissions.

⁵⁴ Petroleum Industry Act 2021, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria; MO Akinkugbe, 'The Petroleum Industry Act 2021 and Environmental Governance in Nigeria' (2022) 15(1) *Nigerian Journal of Energy and Environmental Law* 67.

- II. By reducing GHGs (like CO₂, Methane, and black carbon), it also reduces air pollutants that harm human health (PM_{2.5}, ozone, NO₂, SO₂).
- III. Furthermore, by promoting low-carbon energy, transport, and industry, the Act indirectly tackle urban and soot pollution.
- IV. The Act aims at achieving net-zero target by 2060, this measure when achieved would drastically improve ambient and indoor air quality.

As ambitious as this Act appears, it is however challenged by data scarcity, political will and overlapping with other laws like NESREA, resulting in conflict or duplication⁵⁵.

(e) Control measures under the Common Law

Air quality control under the common law is not usually framed in the same way as statutory or regulatory approaches (like NESREA regulations). Instead, the common law provides private rights of action and remedies that individuals or communities can use when air pollution interferes with their health, property, or enjoyment of land. The main common law principles relevant to air quality control includes:

1. Nuisance - both private and public nuisance

(a) Private nuisance, which arises where a person's use of their land causes substantial and unreasonable interference with another's uses or enjoyment of their land. Smoke, fumes, dust, or noxious gases fall under this head. In the case of *Sturges v. Bridgman*⁵⁶, the court held that an activity lawful in itself may become a nuisance if it interferes with neighbours' rights.

(b) Public nuisance: This concerns acts that interfere with rights common to the general public, including air quality. Example, emission of harmful gases that affects a whole community may be restrained or sanction as a public nuisance. In Nigeria, public nuisance is also criminalized under sections 234-245 of the Criminal Code Act.

2. Negligence

Where pollution (e.g., industrial emissions, flaring, or dust release) causes foreseeable harm to persons or property, an action may lie in negligence. To succeed, claimants must prove duty of care, breach, causation, and damage. For example, a company emitting hazardous smoke without adequate control measures could be liable if it causes respiratory illness.⁵⁷

3. Trespass

Although less common for air pollution, trespass may apply if pollutants like particulate matter or soot physically enter another's land. However, modern courts prefer nuisance to handle such cases, but trespass is relevant where physical invasion can be shown.

⁵⁵ Climate Change Act 2021, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria.

⁵⁶ (1879) 11 Ch D 852.

⁵⁷ See *Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) v. Farah* (1995) NWLR (Pt. 382) 148; *Donoghue v. Stevenson* (1932) AC 562; *Cambridge Water Co. v. Eastern Counties Leather Plc* (1994) 2 AC 264.

4. Strict liability (Rule in Ryland v. Flecher)⁵⁸

The principle is simple, if a person brings onto land something likely to cause mischief if it escapes (e.g., chemicals, gas, smoke), they are strictly liable for damage caused by its escape. This principle has been invoked in environmental cases where dangerous substances escape into the environment, affecting air quality. In *Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) Ltd. V. Amaro*,⁵⁹ the Court of Appeal applied the principle of strict liability where oil spilled from Shell's facilities. While not strictly about air emissions, the reasoning extends to gas flaring and release of hazardous gases, since these are "dangerous things" brought onto land.

5. Equitable remedies

Courts may grant injunctions to restrain ongoing or threatened pollution and may also award damages for past harm caused by poor air quality. In *Gbemre v. Shell Petroleum Development Company Nigeria Ltd*,⁶⁰ the Federal High Court issued an injunction restraining Shell and NNPC from further gas flaring in Iwherekan Community, Delta State.

In common law jurisdictions, including Nigeria, courts have used these doctrines to indirectly enforce air quality standards even before specific environmental laws existed.

4. CHALLENGES OF THE REGULATORY FRAMEWORKS FOR AIR POLLUTION CONTROL, AND STRATEGIES FOR REDRESS

The challenges cover both the international and domestic regulatory mechanisms. For a more pragmatic approach, it will serve the interest of the paper better to discuss them seriatim.

4.1 Challenges of global Enforceability of Air Pollution:

Tackling air pollution globally is one of the toughest environmental challenges because it crosses borders, involves multiple sectors, and is tied to economic growth. The key challenges include:

(a) Transboundary nature of pollution

Air pollution (e.g., fine particulates, ozone precursors, sulfur dioxide, black carbon) do not respect national borders. Regional agreements (like the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution in Europe) show it can be managed, but globally there is no binding framework covering all pollutants. For example, dust storms in the Sahara affect air quality in Europe.

(b) Fragmented international frameworks

⁵⁸ (1868) LR 3 HL 330.

⁵⁹ (2000) 10 NWLR (Pt. 675) 248.

⁶⁰ (2005) AHRLR 151.

Unlike climate change (Paris Agreement), there is no single global treaty on air pollution. Existing measures are piecemeal. For example, the WHO sets Air Quality Guidelines, but they are not legally binding; UNEP promotes initiatives (e.g., Climate and Clean Air Coalition) but participation is voluntary.

(c) Conflicting development priorities

Developing countries often prioritize economic growth, industrialization, and energy access over strict air quality controls. Developing countries including Nigeria heavily rely on coal, biomass, and petroleum fuels and makes strict measures on air quality politically and economically difficult.

(d) Weak enforcement and governance

Even where national laws exist, enforcement is often poor due to corruption, lack of capacity, or political resistance. Environmental agencies in many countries are under-resourced, in contrast, polluting industries (e.g., oil, coal, transport) may have strong political influence.

(e) Technology and infrastructure gaps

Advanced technologies (scrubbers, catalytic converters, clean fuels, air quality monitors) are costly and out of the reach of many low-and middle- income countries including Nigeria to access. Also, these countries have weak monitoring networks, poor data and weak accountability.

(f) Funding and economic constraints

Air pollution control requires large investments in clean energy, transport, industry, and waste systems. Developing countries often depends on international finance, which is limited and focused more on climate change than air quality.

(g) Weak institutional capacity of NESREA

NESREA (National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency is underfunded and understaffed. Furthermore, Nigeria has only a few functional air quality monitoring networks, mostly donor-supported, concentrated in Lagos, Abuja and Port Harcourt. Also, there is inadequate and reliable data that has made enforcement weak.

(h) Overlapping and conflicting mandates

Several agencies (NESREA, NUPRC, Ministry of Environment, State Environmental Agencies, NIMASA for shipping emissions) have unclear or overlapping roles. This causes jurisdictional conflicts and regulatory loopholes, allowing polluters to exploit the gaps.

5. CONCLUSION

Air pollution in Nigeria persists largely due to weak enforcement, overlapping laws, poor monitoring, and corruption, despite the presence of modern regulatory frameworks. These challenges mirror global difficulties in balancing industrial growth with environmental sustainability. Addressing them requires harmonized laws, stronger institutions, effective monitoring, economic incentives, and active community participation with firm political will and international cooperation, Nigeria can improve air quality regulation and align with global best practices for sustainable development.